

Heart Disease Prediction with an Amharic Chatbot

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Abstract: Predicting the onset of heart or cardiac diseases is a critical challenge in modern medicine, with approximately One Hundred Seventy person death per minute attributed to heart disease. The vast amount of healthcare data underscores the importance of data science in extracting meaningful insights. Multiple data model strategies are explored to evaluate the likelihood of patients developing heart disease and categorize risk levels using chosen classifiers. Data from Menelik Hospitals in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, is utilized, and multiple performance metrics such as sensitivity, accuracy, AUC, specificity, ROC curve, and F1-score are employed for evaluation. The outcome is a Heart Disease Prediction integrated with an Amharic Chatbot. Additionally, the Random Forest algorithm emerges as the top performer, achieving an impressive 99% accuracy for predicting heart disease. Simultaneously, the Amharic Chatbot, using the Feed Forward Neural Network Model, achieves commendable performance with 92.88% accuracy, facilitating user-friendly communication in Amharic and promoting cultural diversity.

Keywords: Amharic Chatbot, Heart Disease Prediction, NLP , FFNN

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Introduction

Globally, heart attacks and cardiovascular diseases, such as Congestive Heart Failure (CHF), are the leading causes of death. The World Health Organization reported that in 2015, cardiovascular diseases accounted for 17.7 million deaths, or 31% of global mortality, with 82% occurring in developing countries. Additionally, 17 million of these deaths were among individuals under 70, highlighting premature death among the working-age population. Stroke and coronary heart disease were the primary contributors, causing 6.7 million and 7.4 million deaths, respectively. Addressing risk factors like hypertension, high cholesterol, smoking, poor diet, and lack of exercise is crucial in reducing these numbers[11]. In Ethiopia, Congestive Heart Failure (CHF) has emerged as the leading cause of death, claiming the lives of approximately 170 Ethiopians daily[1]. This stark figure not only aligns with the global trend of cardiovascular diseases but also highlights specific national challenges, with hypertensive heart disease (11%), stroke (34%), and ischemic heart disease (45%) being the primary culprits, alongside other factors contributing to the remaining 10%. This scenario underscores the critical necessity for targeted public health strategies and healthcare interventions within Ethiopia. Addressing the root causes of CHF, enhancing access to quality healthcare, and fostering healthy lifestyle choices are im-

perative for reducing the cardiovascular disease burden and significantly improving the health outcomes of the Ethiopian population[2]. Amharic, the official working language of Ethiopia, plays a pivotal role both culturally and administratively, with over 32.4 million native speakers by 2018 and more than 25.1 million second-language speakers by 2019, totaling over 57.5 million speakers[3]. This makes Amharic not only the most widely spoken language in Ethiopia but also the second most widely spoken Semitic language in the world, after Arabic[4]. Its significance extends beyond mere communication; Amharic is a vital carrier of the nation's cultural heritage, history, and identity, deeply embedded in literature, education, and media. As Ethiopia's linguistic landscape continues to evolve, Amharic remains at the heart of the nation's socio-cultural and intellectual fabric, bridging the rich historical past with a dynamic and evolving future, and underscoring its critical role in the country's ongoing development and unity.

Motivation

The integration of machine learning and deep learning technologies for heart disease prediction, alongside the innovative use of an Amharic chatbot, represents a transformative step in personalized healthcare and linguistic inclusivity. This approach leverages machine learning algorithms to analyze key risk factors like age, blood pressure, and cholesterol, predicting heart disease based on patterns from historical health data, while deep learning models power the chatbot to facilitate natural conversations in Amharic. By providing a user-friendly tool for early detection and raising awareness of heart disease risks, this initiative bridges critical gaps in health education and services for Amharic-speaking populations. It showcases how advanced AI can overcome language barriers and improve health outcomes by making sophisticated health assessments accessible to everyone, without requiring users to navigate complex medical terminology. This dual-technology approach not only promotes preventive care but also highlights the potential of AI to democratize health information. For Amharic-speaking communities, it signifies a step toward equitable health access, ensuring that cutting-edge healthcare solutions are available to all, regardless of language or location. As this technology evolves, it holds the promise of setting a new global standard for personalized, inclusive healthcare.

Significance

The research presents a significant breakthrough in heart disease detection and prevention through the integration of a machine learning predictive model with an Amharic chatbot. By offering accurate heart disease risk predictions, it promotes early intervention and proactive health management, reducing the prevalence and severity of the disease. The inclusion of an Amharic chatbot represents a major advancement, making essential health information more accessible and understandable to Amharic speakers, thus enhancing public health literacy. This approach not only enables timely medical advice and interventions—potentially saving lives—but also increases healthcare system efficiency by providing culturally sensitive education and empowering individuals to make informed health decisions.

Literature Review

The review will examine various methodologies and tools employed, proposed solutions, accuracy scores achieved, and models utilized in these studies. Our objective is to provide a comprehensive overview of the research landscape in this field, with a focus on key findings and insights that have emerged from these efforts.

In their 2023 study, Kavya TN and colleagues developed a data-driven prediction model for early heart attack detection using various machine learning algorithms. These included Logistic Regression, Random Forest, K-Nearest Neighbors, Naive Bayes, Decision Tree, SVM (Linear, Polynomial, Gaussian, Sigmoid), Bagging, AdaBoost, Gradient Boost, and XGBoost classifiers. Among these, the Random Forest classifier achieved the highest accuracy of 87.9%. The study aimed to assist in early heart disease diagnosis for high-risk individuals based on medical criteria[5].

Prasher, Nelson, and Hariharan (2023) used a Kaggle dataset with 1,025 instances and 14 variables to predict heart disease. They tested K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN), Multi-Layer Perceptron, Decision Tree, and REPTree algorithms, evaluating them on accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. The KNN classifier achieved the highest accuracy of 99.7%, outperforming the other models[6].

J. Nirmal Jothi et al. (2022) developed an AI-based humanoid chatbot for medical applications, capable of answering queries and predicting heart disease. The chatbot uses Natural Language Processing (NLP) and an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) trained on a JSON dataset, achieving over 90% accuracy[7].

Hema et al. (2023) developed a disease prediction system using machine learning and NLP. The study compared Naive Bayes, Decision Trees, and Random Forest models to predict diseases from symptoms. The system uses NLP to process user input, with Random Forest achieving the highest accuracy at 98.17%. The solution includes a chatbot interface to provide immediate disease predictions, reducing patient anxiety[8].

Anand et al. (2023) developed a hybrid chatbot for women's self-help groups in rural India. The chatbot combines AI and rule-based methods, offering a multilingual platform to enhance digital engagement and financial management through the AmritaSREE app. It uses Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) for business-related queries and a rule-based system for support. The focus is on its design, implementation, and potential benefits, with no accuracy metrics provided[9].

Research Gap

Research on Amharic language chatbots reveals a significant gap in heart disease prediction tools for Amharic speakers. While many healthcare chatbots exist in English, few cater to Amharic, Ethiopia's official language. Our research addresses this by developing a heart disease prediction chatbot tailored to Amharic speakers. Unlike other studies that rely on online datasets, we used original data from Menelik Hospital in Addis Ababa, ensuring a more relevant analysis.

3. Methodology

Data Cleaning, is vital for ensuring a dataset's reliability by addressing issues like missing values, out-of-range data, and noise[12]. Though time-consuming, it enhances accuracy for analysis. Our preprocessing includes handling missing values, correlation analysis, standardization, normalization, and feature extraction to reduce dimensionality, preparing the dataset for analysis and model development.

Data Collection

The dataset used in this study was obtained from Menelik Hospital in Addis Ababa and consists of approximately 9,000 patient records, each containing 16 attributes such as demographic information, medical history, and diagnostic test results. These attributes were selected based on their relevance to heart disease prediction.

Data Preprocessing

Data preprocessing involved cleaning the dataset by handling missing values, detecting outliers, and normalizing the data[13]. Feature selection techniques, such as correlation analysis, were employed to identify the most relevant predictors for heart disease. Attributes like age, cholesterol levels, ECG readings, and chest pain were identified as key features for the prediction model.

Characteristics of Amharic Language Amharic, As the official working language of Ethiopia, Amharic stands out within the Afroasiatic language family due to its unique script, Ge'ez or Fidel. This script operates as an abugida, where each character represents a consonant-vowel combination and is written from left to right. The language's phonetic system is characterized by the use of ejective consonants and a wide range of vowel sounds. Its vocabulary is a blend of indigenous terms and loanwords from languages like Italian, English, and Arabic, reflecting Ethiopia's long history of cultural interactions. In terms of grammar, Amharic is particularly intricate, with verb conjugations that encode tense, aspect, mood, and subject-object relationships. Nouns are gendered and can take on different forms to indicate case, though not to the extent seen in some other languages. Amharic generally follows a Subject-Object-Verb (SOV) word order but allows for flexibility based on sentence emphasis. Despite regional dialectal differences influencing pronunciation and vocabulary, Amharic continues to play a crucial role in Ethiopia's national identity and is widely used in administration, education, media, and daily communication. The writing system consists of 33 core characters organized into six orders, with the first five representing consonant-vowel pairs and the sixth functioning as a consonant or vowel, yielding 231 primary characters. Additionally, over 40 special characters, often denoting labialization, are also

part of the script. Unlike other non-Latin scripts like Arabic, Amharic characters are not joined and lack diacritical dots, despite having a cursive appearance.

Model Selection Heart Disease Prediction

Several machine learning models were evaluated, including Logistic Regression, Decision Trees, Random Forest, and Support Vector Machines (SVM). Random Forest was selected for its high accuracy and ability to handle complex interactions between variables. The model was trained on 70% of the dataset and tested on the remaining 30%, achieving an accuracy of 99%.

Model Selection Amharic Chatbot

Model selection involves choosing the most suitable algorithm or model design to solve a specific problem by evaluating various models based on criteria like accuracy, generalization ability, and computational efficiency. This process is crucial for developing effective machine learning systems, as the chosen model significantly impacts the solution's success[10].

Figure 3.1 Feedforward Neural Network

The chatbot was developed using Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques to process Amharic text. A Feedforward Neural Network (FFNN) was employed for intent recognition and response generation. The chatbot was designed to ask users about their symptoms, provide heart disease risk assessments, and offer advice on seeking medical help. The JSON structure for defining chatbot intents, patterns, and responses represents **functional requirements** for each feature:

1. Symptom Checker:
 - Recognizes user queries like "What are the symptoms of heart disease?"
 - Responds with: "Common symptoms include chest pain, shortness of breath, and fatigue."
2. Risk Assessment:
 - Allows users to input health data (e.g., age, cholesterol) to assess heart disease risk.
 - Provides personalized risk feedback based on inputs.
3. Treatment Information:
 - Responds to queries like "What treatments are available for heart disease?"
 - Provides information on medications, procedures, and lifestyle adjustments.
4. Preventive Measures:
 - Offers guidance on lifestyle changes (e.g., diet, exercise) to reduce heart disease risk.
 - Answers prevention-related questions.
5. Emergency Guidance:
 - Provides immediate advice for heart-related emergencies, such as "What should I do if I think I'm having a heart attack?"

- Instructs users when to seek urgent medical care.

Architectural Design: involves creating a blueprint for how a system will be structured and organized. It outlines the major components of the system, how they interact, and how the system will be deployed. This phase sets the foundation for the detailed design and implementation of the software

Figure 3.2 Architecture Design

Work Flow

A workflow refers to the sequence of steps, tasks, or activities that are necessary to complete a particular process or achieve a specific outcome. In the context of the heart disease prediction with an Amharic chatbot, the outlined architectural framework is as follows:

The Amharic chatbot for heart disease prediction operates by first interacting with users who input their health queries in Amharic. The chatbot processes these inputs using an Intent.json file to detect relevant keywords. Based on the identified keywords, the chatbot offers two options: users can either choose to fill out a form for personalized data entry or receive a predefined response if their input is general. If the form is chosen, users input specific health-related data. This information is then processed using a Random Forest Model to predict the likelihood of heart disease. Once the prediction is made, the chatbot displays the result, indicating the user's risk level. To ensure accurate predictions, the chatbot also preprocesses user text through tokenization, normalization, stemming, stop word removal, and bag-of-words techniques. The system is further enhanced by training a Feedforward Neural Network with this processed data to improve its predictive capabilities over time.

Figure 3.3 Work flow

4 Evaluation

4.1 Heart Prediction Model Performance

The Random Forest model outperformed other machine learning algorithms, achieving an accuracy of 99% in predicting heart disease risk. Feature importance analysis revealed that ECG readings, chest pain, and fasting blood sugar levels were the most influential predictors.

Model	Acc.	Prec.	Rec.	Spec.	F1	C.Error	R.Time
Decision Tree	0.98	0.99	0.99	0.97	0.99	0.02	0.04
Random Forest	0.99	1.00	0.99	1.00	0.99	0.01	0.56
Bayesian	0.99	1.00	0.99	1.00	0.99	0.01	0.02
SVM	0.77	0.80	0.86	0.58	0.83	0.23	2.41
KNN	0.78	0.82	0.85	0.63	0.83	0.22	0.23
Neural Network	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.01	3.31
Logistic Regr	0.98	1.00	0.98	1.00	0.99	0.02	0.11
XGBoost	0.99	1.00	0.99	1.00	0.99	0.01	0.19

Table 4.1 Performance Metrics

4.1.1 Identifying Key Predictors Using the RF

Using the Random Forest (RF) method, we identified the most important predictors of heart disease through feature importance analysis. The Gini approach, as shown in Figure 9, ranked the significance of 16 features, highlighting the key factors influencing heart disease risk.

Figure 4.1 Feature Importance Score

4.1.2 Training and Test Accuracy

Figure 4.2 shows the model's learning curves. The "train random forest" function trains and evaluates a Random Forest model, calculating training and test accuracy. It splits the dataset into training and testing sets, then trains the model and assesses accuracy using the "accuracy score" function, helping evaluate the model's ability to generalize to new data.

Figure 4.2 Training and Test Accuracy

4.2 Chatbot Evaluation

Various performance metrics are used to evaluate chatbot performance throughout different phases, following industry standards[14]. Loss is a key metric that measures the errors in a machine learning model during training and validation, indicating its performance after each optimization iteration[15]. Accuracy quantifies the model's overall performance across all classes, calculated as the ratio of correct predictions to total predictions, making it useful when all classes are equally significant. Precision measures the proportion of true positive predictions among all predicted positives, while recall assesses the completeness of the model by evaluating the proportion of true positives identified[16].

4.2.1 Evaluation on Training Data

After training the model on intents.json, we evaluate its performance by comparing its predictions to the actual labels in the training set. This helps assess how well the model has learned and identifies areas for improvement.

Parameter Name	Value
Epoch	300
Activation	ELU
Batch Size	12
Optimizer	Adam
Learning Rate	0.001

Table 4.1 Parameter Configuration

FeedForwardNN model accomplished the accuracy of Accuracy 92.88% according to the parameter configuration depicted on the table 5.5 and the loss value of this model is 0.0039.

Evaluation Matrix	Percentage (%)
F-Score	92.97
Recall	92.88
Precision	93.76
Accuracy	92.88

Table 4.2 Performance Evaluation

The accuracy and loss of both training and test values for the Feed-Forward NN model were evaluated using metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score. These metrics assessed the chatbot’s ability to accurately classify and retrieve relevant responses to Amharic user queries. The effectiveness of intent classification directly influenced response generation, with the model’s proficiency measured on a designated testing dataset.

Figure 4.3 Accuracy value

Figure 4.4 Training Loss epoch

We conducted experiments to assess the performance of different activation functions in our FeedForwardNN model. The results showed that the Exponential Linear Unit (ELU) activation function achieved the highest performance metrics.

Activation Function	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1
ELU	92.88	93.88	92.88	92.97
ReLU	89.14	91.98	89.14	89.86
Swish	88.58	90.87	88.58	88.94
Softmax	91.5	92.95	91.5	91.68

Table 4.3 Activation Functions

The results showed that the Exponential Linear Unit (ELU) activation function achieved the highest performance metrics.

$$ELU(x) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} x \text{ if } x > 0 \\ \alpha(e^x - 1) \text{ if } x \leq 0 \end{array} \right\} \quad 5.4$$

Implementation

The implementation phase involves coding the chatbot according to the design specifications and architectural framework. This phase includes the development of NLP components to handle Amharic language inputs, integration of the Random Forest predictive model, and setting up the chatbot interface for user interaction. Key steps in the implementation include:

- Developing the core functionality for intent recognition and response generation: This involves utilizing Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques to understand and process user inputs in Amharic. The chatbot

needs to identify user intents accurately and generate appropriate responses.

- Integrating the form submission feature to collect user data: This step includes designing and implementing forms that users can fill out with relevant heart information. This data collection is crucial for the predictive model. The forms should be user-friendly and support Amharic language inputs.
- Implementing the machine learning model for heart disease prediction: The Random Forest model, trained on a dataset of relevant health indicators, needs to be integrated into the chatbot. This involves loading the pre-trained model and using it to make predictions based on the data provided by users. The model's predictions should then be communicated back to the user in an understandable and actionable manner.

When a user inputs the keyword "More" after completing their interaction with the Health Disease Prediction form, it triggers the system to present an additional feature or service. Specifically, upon entering "More," the system unveils a

A screenshot of a web form titled 'HEART DISEASE PREDICTION'. The form is set against a green background and contains several input fields for user data. At the top, there are radio buttons for gender: 'ግብ' (Male) and 'ሴት' (Female). Below are input fields for: 'እድሜ' (Age) with value 56; 'የልብ ምት' (Heart rate) with value 93; 'ሲስቶሊክ የደም ግፊት' (Systolic blood pressure) with value 120; 'ዲያስቶሊክ የደም ግፊት' (Diastolic blood pressure) with value 88; 'የሙቀት መጠን' (Temperature) with value 36; 'የሙተንፈሻ መጠን' (Respiration rate) with value 22; 'እክስጅን' (Oxygen) with value 99; 'ክብደት' (Weight) with value 163; 'ኮሌስትሮል' (Cholesterol) with value 155; 'የደም ስኬር' (Blood sugar) with value 145; 'የደረት ሀመም' (Diabetes) with a dropdown menu set to 'No'; 'ሱስ' (Smoking) with a dropdown menu set to 'No'; 'ከሌተሰብ የሚወረስ' (Family history) with a dropdown menu set to 'No'; and 'ECG' with a dropdown menu set to 'Normal'. A 'PREDICT' button is located at the bottom of the form.

new API interface dedicated to heart disease prediction. This mechanism allows for a seamless transition between services, enabling the user to access further specialized health assessments without the need for complex navigation. The keyword "More" acts as a simple, intuitive command that broadens the user's interaction with the system, facilitating access to more in-depth health analyses or predictions within the same platform.

After the user inputs critical information such as Sex, Age, PR, and SBP,.. the system analyzes this data to provide a health assessment. The output indicates that the patient is likely to have heart failure, suggesting a significant correlation between the entered parameters and potential heart health risks. This result underscores the importance of further medical evaluation and intervention.

Conclusion

The development of an Amharic chatbot for predicting heart disease, using data collected from Ethiopia. Various supervised learning algorithms were tested, including Logistic Regression, Decision Trees, Support Vector Machine (SVM), Bayesian Network, k-Nearest Neighbor, Neural Network, and XGBoost. Among these, the Random Forest model performed best, achieving an accuracy of 99%. The chatbot, integrated into the heart disease prediction framework, employs Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques and a Feedforward Neural Network to accurately interpret user queries in Amharic, achieving a 92.88% accuracy. Despite these promising results, further research is required to enhance the model with more diverse datasets, explore advanced machine learning techniques, and improve the chatbot's NLP capabilities. This work represents a significant step toward addressing healthcare challenges in Ethiopia by leveraging machine learning and NLP technologies to improve healthcare accessibility and outcomes for diverse populations.

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